

SEARCH FOR DIMENSIONS OF CONSUMER NEEDS: DIFFERENCES AMONG GENERATIVE TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this study are to discover underlying dimensions of consumer needs with generative tools and to compare the effect of a tool in eliciting consumer needs by comparing results obtained by different tools. Three previous projects of searching consumer needs are utilized as the data for this study. The projects were about university students' needs on devices supporting studying; SNS (social network service) based health care service design for teenagers, and health care service design for local hospitals. Three dimensions are found and the combinations of the three produce eight types of consumer needs. The three dimensional eight type framework of consumer needs is applied for comparing differences among generative tools. Workbooks and 3-D modeling proved to be good tools in eliciting functional and improvable needs, while collages turned out to be good tools for revealing emotional needs. The younger generation reveals their willingness to extend their capabilities and be empowered, while adults' scopes are much narrower within the boundary of improvements in their current situations.

Keywords: consumer needs, generative tools, latent needs, dimensions of a need

INTRODUCTION

Successful human-centered design demands profound knowledge of consumers and their needs. In order to understand consumers' real needs, a designer's goal is not to be led solely by consumers' expressed need but to amaze them by anticipating and fulfilling their unarticulated needs (Hamel and Prahalad, 1994). To achieve this, designers must gain consumer insights with a bottom-up approach that

leverages insights into the behaviors, perceptions and needs of consumers by involving them as true partners in the design process.

Traditional approaches for identifying consumer needs are adopting a very rational perspective and focusing too much on explicit verbal needs with top-down frameworks. Non-traditional approaches allow us to glean grass-root insights into both articulated and unarticulated consumer needs with bottom-up frameworks.

Bottom-up grass-root approaches need to go beyond knowing what people think, say, do, and use. Asking what people think and listening to what people say gives us only what they are able to express in words, which reveals explicit needs. Watching what people do and seeing what they use gives us observable information. Providing make toolkits for expressing people's thoughts, feelings, and dreams allows us to empathize with them and to discover unknown, undefined, and unanticipated needs (Sanders, 1999). Make tools are a visual language that people can use to express feelings and ideas that are hard to express in words.

This study aims at searching for dimensions of consumer needs with Sanders' generative tools (2000, 2001). The data underpinning this paper draw on several sources of the author's past generative tools studies. Each study created a generative toolkit that is specific to extract both articulated and unarticulated consumer needs on each theme. Consumer needs collected through several studies are repeatedly reviewed to find common dimensions behind the consumer's needs. Once the common dimensions are revealed, results from different generative tools are

compared to investigate the differences among various tools in searching consumer needs.

CONSUMER NEEDS

The concept of needs is a very complex psychological phenomenon. A need is concerned with a lack of something that is wanted (Holt, et al., 1984). It is defined as a gap between the real and the ideal conditions (Reviere, et. al., 1996), the discrepancy between the existing and the wanted situation that may or may not be recognized (Holt, et al., 1984), and the statement, in an individual's words, of a benefit that the person gets (Cohen, 1995). In the design process, understanding consumer needs is an essential stage. Successful new products and services are those which meet a specific consumer need (Griffin, et al., 2009; Leonard and Rayport, 1997).

There are many different levels of consumer needs. Holt et al. (1984) classify customer needs into existing and future needs by the time-oriented classification and into emotional and rational needs by the emotion-oriented classification. *Existing* needs are of a conscious nature and therefore relatively easy to discover, while *future* needs are those that do not exist at present but will materialize in the future. *Emotional* or non-rational needs are concerned with novelty, style, color, and other characteristics of an esthetic nature, while *rational* needs are concerned with function and use.

The multiplicity of levels of consumer needs and the relative inability of consumers to express those needs are emphasized by Sanders (1992, 1999). The levels of need expression are classified into explicit, observable, tacit, and latent needs. *Explicit* needs are those that people can express in words and, therefore can be obtained by listening to what they say or interpreting what they express and make inferences about what they think. *Observable* needs are displayed in action and can be determined through observational methods. *Tacit* needs are conscious needs that people are unable to express in words, so that we need to empathize with them to understand how they feel. *Latent* needs are subconscious, possibly dormant needs that people are unable to express in words and are not recognizable until the

future, so that we need to see and appreciate what they dream and empathize with them at the deepest levels of their expression by establishing resonance with them using special tools.

Latent needs are also defined as those that many consumers recognize as important in the final product but do not or are not able to articulate in advance (Ulrich and Eppinger, 2008). Tacit or latent needs are also often referred as *hidden* (Goffin and Lemke, 2004), *subtle* and *subconscious* (Deszca et al., 1999), *unarticulated* (Leonard and Rayport, 1997), and *unrecognized hidden* and *future* (Kärkkäinen et al., 2001) needs.

The different ways of accessing consumer needs have evolved over time from focusing on what people say and think through questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups, observing what people do and use through empathic design or ethnographic methods, and focusing on what people make with creativity based research tools provided to the participants.

GENERATIVE TOOLS

Generative tools are make tools provided for ordinary consumers in the generative phase of the design development process in order to discover unknown, undefined, and unanticipated consumer needs (Sanders, 1999, 2000, 2001). A large number of components are put together into 'toolkits', from which participants select them and create 'artifacts' that express their thoughts, feelings, ideas, and dreams. The resulting artifacts are extremely effective in expressing participants' stories. The stories tell us not only understanding and misunderstanding things, events, and places, but also feelings, dreams, fears, and aspirations.

The generative technique is designed with a four-step framework: 1) immersion/sensitization 2) activation of feelings and memories 3) dreaming and 4) bisociation and expression (Sanders, 2001). Several applications of this technique to Korean consumers reveal that the fourth step, bisociation and expression, is not useful to bring expression to the ideas participants have developed up until the third step (Hwang and Kim, 2010; Kim, 2009; Kim and Hwang, 2011).

The immersion/ sensitization step lasts about one week and takes place in the natural contexts of the participants with a daily self-documentation tool as a workbook format that makes the participants attune to details of their activities and experiences they might normally take for granted, and prime their forgotten memories. The next three steps take place in a face-to-face group meeting with 4 to 5 participants at a time. Two to three groups of participants are good enough to collect consumer needs within a subject matter. The toolkits designed to evoke and activate related memories and feelings in the second step are predominantly visual such as pictures, words, and symbols to make collages. The third, the revised final, step is for dreaming about future or ideal experience by expressing desires, wants, and hopes in a 3-dimensional modeling. A large number of components are put into a 3-D modeling toolkit such as color clay, various textures of materials like textiles, plastics, and polystyrol, various textures of strings like metal, rubber, and wool, various sizes and thicknesses of color papers, various sizes of cotton balls, polystyrol balls, and buttons, various thicknesses and materials of boards like clear or colored plastic, hard board, and thin metal, scissors, cutters, glues, tapes, color pens and pencils, and the like. Refining the 3-D modeling toolkits is specific to each project's purpose. The 3-D modeling toolkits are found to be good for accessing participants' unspoken dreams for the future. This final step invites them to bring expression to the ideas they have incubated and developed up until that moment with intuitions, images, and bodily feelings.

The revised three steps that proved to be effective from several generative tools projects in Korea provide a broad spectrum of consumer needs within a subject matter in multiple layers and levels. The visual nature of the tools clearly helps to discover conscious and subconscious consumer needs that the participants are unable to express in words. Visualization has been proved as a useful approach for product development (Olausson and Ming, 2009). Use of multiple dimensions of visual objects can stimulate multiple senses which are linked to the episodic and procedural memory (Tulving, 1985).

METHOD AND MATERIALS

The author has applied generative tools to several studies for searching consumer needs on various design themes such as an imaging device, a refrigerator, a kitchen, learning, LED lighting designs for offices and for commercial spaces, SNS (social network services) based health care service design for teenagers, health care service design for local hospitals, and building energy conservation in Korea since 2009. Among them this study adopts three studies for accomplishing dual purposes: one is to search the dimensions of consumer needs and the other is to compare the differences among the generative tools in eliciting consumer needs.

The three themes of searching consumer needs are devices supporting university students' learning, SNS (social network services) based health care service design for teenagers, and health care service design for local hospitals. The generative tools in each study are composed of workbooks for the immersion or sensitization step, collages for the activation step, and 3-D modeling for the dreaming stage. Workbooks were delivered to each participant's home or office and collected before the group session days. Collaging and 3-D modeling were accomplished in the group sessions. Table 1 indicates the participants and the time of each study.

Theme Item	Theme A: Learning	Theme B: SNS health service	Theme C: Local hospital
Year	2009	2010	2011
Participants	9 university students	8 high school students	10 adults
Workbook period	6 days (Sept. 19~24)	5 days (Dec. 9~13)	5 days (Feb. 1~5)
Group session days	1 st : Sep. 30 2 nd : October 1	1 st : Dec. 26 2 nd : Dec. 29	1 st : Feb. 15, afternoon 2 nd : evening

Table 1. Data of this study

The three studies started with the workbook self-documentation periods and the finished workbooks were collected before the group session days. The group session started with individual storytelling about

each participant’s workbook and gathered together for fulfilling the second and the third steps of the generative tools procedure as indicated in (Table 2). The activation tools were images, words, symbols, color pens, and a background on which to work for collages. Each participant had storytelling time with his/her collage. The dreaming tools were various sizes, shapes, and colors of materials for 3-D modeling. The creator of 3-D modeling had another storytelling time to tell stories associated with the artifact. The group session ended with 10 minutes of wrap-up free talking among the participants. The generative tools for the three studies are shown in (Table 3).

Step	Action	Unit	Time
1	Workbook storytelling	Individual	30 min.
2	Collaging	Individual	30 min.
	Collage storytelling	Group	20 min.
	Intermission		10 min.
3	3-D modeling	Individual	30 min.
	3-D model storytelling	Group	20 min.
	Wrap-up free talking	Group	10 min.

Table 2. A timetable for a group session

Theme Tool	Learning	SNS health service	Local hospital
Workbook			
Collage			
3-D modeling			

Table 3. Generative tools for the three studies

All the group sessions were held in a one-way mirrored room that is typically used for a focus group

interview. All the say and make activities were voice and video recorded. The resulting data were huge in quantity and varied in quality from workbooks, short background questionnaires, collages, 3-D modeling, to storytelling about workbooks, collages, and 3-D modeling. An excel file for each participant was constructed with everything that was said and made. An intense and time-consuming content analysis was followed in line with the three steps of generative data analysis suggested in Visser et al. (2005): 1) fixate on the data 2) search and be surprised and 3) find patterns and create an overall view. The purposes of the searching and finding patterns from the data were to find consumer needs on each theme or topic of the study.

DIMENSIONS OF CONSUMER NEEDS

The statements containing any clues of consumer needs were highlighted and mutually exclusive need statements were extracted. A close examination of the extracted consumer needs across the three themes was repeatedly conducted to find common dimensions underlying consumer needs. This was an intensively time-consuming process to discover the common dimensions of the consumer’s needs. Meanwhile, dimensions underlying consumer needs across the three materials were gradually revealed. The first two dimensions were relatively easy to discover, but the third one took much longer to discover.

The first dimension is related with the *source* of a consumer need that is either *internal* or *external*. The second dimension is related with the *utility* of a consumer need such as *functional* or *emotional*. The third dimension is related with the *solution* of a consumer need such as *improvable* or *empowering*. Internal needs are originated from an individual and external needs are originated from outside of the self. Functional needs are those pursuing functional outcomes such as durability, usability, or usefulness, while emotional needs are those pursuing emotional experience such as positive feelings or joyful experience. Improvable needs are related with the hope to be better than the current situation, while empowering needs are those enhancing capability levels of an individual in an innovative way. The three dimensions discovered through the search are depicted in (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dimensions of consumer needs

Consumer needs are supposed to be composed with these three dimensions. This is represented with double circles with a horizontal and a vertical axis as in (Figure 2) to show the structure of the dimensions graphically. The vertical axis indicates the source of a consumer need either internal or external. Those needs that are seemingly originated from one self are expressed in the above half of the diagram, while those seemingly originated from outside of the self are depicted in the bottom. The horizontal axis indicates the utility of a consumer need either functional or emotional. Any needs that seem to be related with functional utility are expressed in the left of the diagram, while those seemingly related with emotional utility are assigned in the right. The double circles indicate the solutions of a consumer need either the improvable in the inner circle or the empowering in the outer circle. Those needs seemingly related with improvable outcomes are depicted in the inner circle, while those seemingly related with enhancing one's capability are expressed in the outer circle.

The three dimensions divide consumer needs into eight types as indicated in (Figure 2) such that the four types of consumer needs are revealed in the four spaces in the inner circle and another four types are revealed in the four spaces between the two circles. The eight types of consumer needs classified by the three dimensions are *internal functional improvable (IFR)*, *internal functional empowering (IFO)*, *internal emotional improvable (IER)*, *internal emotional empowering (IEO)*, *external functional improvable (XFR)*, *external functional empowering (XFO)*, *external emotional improvable (XER)*, and *external*

emotionally empowering (XEO). The three dimensional eight type framework of consumer needs provides an excellent basis for understanding consumer needs that are purely extracted from a bottom-up approach and for comparing differences in eliciting consumer needs among various tools.

Figure 2. Three dimensional eight type framework of consumer needs

COMPARING DIFFERENT THEMES OF CONSUMER NEEDS

The three dimensional eight type framework of consumer needs is applied to the three themes of consumer needs, i.e., devices supporting university students' learning, SNS based health care service design for teenagers, and health care service design for local hospitals. First, all the consumer needs extracted from the three studies are divided according to the three dimensions as in (Table 4) then, they are divided according to the eight types as in (Table 5) and (Figure 3). Here, the counted numbers of consumer needs per se are not very meaningful, since they reflect completely different natures regarding consumer needs confined within a specific theme. Therefore, the numbers are listed in lighter colors as supplementary information.

University students' needs on devices supporting their learning are more likely to be originated from themselves, functional, and improvable. Teenagers' needs on SNS based health care services are mainly related with internal. The proportions of the emotional and the empowering needs are the highest among the

three themes and groups of participants. Adult consumers' needs on health care services from local hospitals are caused both internally and externally, characterized as slightly more functional than emotional, and focused on improvable solutions. The results indicate that consumer needs on tangible products are more likely to be functional and improvable, while emotional needs tend to be increased for services. Teenagers' show their willingness to be able to manage their health issues and this is indicated in the highest proportion of the empowering needs in (Table 4).

Need dimension		Theme		
		Learning	SNS health service	Local hospital
Source	I Internal	62.1% 280	97.4 % 236	49.8 % 309
	X External	37.9 171	2.6 6	50.2 311
Utility	F Functional	81.8 369	59.8 145	60.6 376
	E Emotional	18.2 82	40.2 97	39.4 244
Solution	R Improvable	95.6 431	65.2 158	98.4 611
	O Empowering	4.4 20	34.8 84	1.6 9
Total		100.0 451	100.0 242	100.0 620

Table 4. Classification of consumer needs into the three dimensions

The eight types of consumer needs are applied to the three studies. University students' needs on devices supporting their learning tend to be either internal or external functional improvable, i.e., IFR or XFR. These two types of consumer needs occupy the majority of their needs. Teenagers' needs on SNS based health care services tend to be mainly internal and those are focused within the functional improvable type. Almost none of the external needs are revealed, while the internal emotional empowering, the internal emotional improvable, and the internal functional empowering are revealed in some way. Adult consumers' needs on health care services from local hospitals tend to be focused within the boundary of the improvable. The willingness to be able to manage their health care at their wish is barely expressed, while the functional improvable needs that

are either internal or external are expressed the most with the supplementary expression of the emotional improvable needs that are either internal or external. These results are graphically represented in (Figure 3).

Theme Need type	Learning	SNS health service	Local hospital
IFR	52.8 % 238	44.6 % 108	25.6 % 159
IFO	1.1 5	13.6 33	1.5 9
IER	6.0 27	19.4 47	22.7 141
IEO	2.2 10	19.8 48	0.0 0
XFR	27.7 125	0.4 1	33.5 208
XFO	0.2 1	1.2 3	0.0 0
XER	9.1 41	0.8 2	16.6 103
XEO	0.9 4	0.0 0	0.0 0
Total	100.0 451	100.0 242	100.0 620

Table 5. Classification of consumer needs into the eight need types

Figure 3. Comparing eight types of consumer needs among the three themes

COMPARING DIFFERENT TOOLS FOR ELICITING CONSUMER NEEDS

The generative tools adopted in the three studies are 5 to 6 days of self-documentation of a workbook, a collage, and a 3-D model which all included a storytelling session. The second research question of this study is to examine the eight types of consumer needs that are elicited with different generative tools and see how different the results among the different tools are. This is analyzed in two ways for each theme of consumer needs. One is to examine the

contribution of each tool on eliciting each type of consumer need and, therefore, each cell in (Table 6) indicates the proportion of a need type elicited with each tool among the total number of consumer needs. The other is to examine the distribution of the eight types of consumer needs that are elicited with each tool, and, therefore, each row in (Table 7) indicates the distribution of the need types elicited with a tool.

COMPARING ACROSS THE TOOLS

The right end columns of (Table 6) indicate that workbooks elicited the largest number of total consumer needs from about a half to more than a half of the total, while collages the second and 3-D modeling last. However, a workbook is designed to be taken ten minutes per day and go on for five to six days, so that it takes about one and a half hours in total, while a collage and 3-D modeling take about 50 minutes each with 30 minutes for making and 20 minutes for storytelling. Consequently, a workbook takes twice the time of the participants than the other two tools. Considering this time span, a collage is the most time efficient tool in eliciting consumer needs. This tendency is most obviously seen in eliciting teenagers' needs in the middle of (Table 6).

Each theme's bottom line in the table indicates the proportion of each type of consumer needs. Theme A shows that consumer needs on tangible devices tend to be functional and improvable with minor emotional needs. The internal functional improvable needs appear regardless of the tools, while slightly more internal emotional needs appeared through collaging. Three-D modeling adds the most obvious need type, IFR. Theme B indicates that workbooks and 3-D modeling produce the IFR type needs of teenagers on SNS based health care services a lot, while collages produce the IER type the most. Theme C shows that workbooks produce the functional improvable types of adult consumers' needs on health care services from local hospitals, while collages and 3-D modeling add up the emotional improvable types.

Theme / Tool	IFR	IFO	IER	IEO	XFR	XFO	XER	XEO	Total	
A	Workbook	24.6	0.9	1.8	0.2	20.6	0.2	5.8	0.2	54.3
		111	4	8	1	93	1	26	1	245
	Collage	16.0	0.0	3.1	2.0	4.9	0.0	2.0	0.7	28.6
		72	0	14	9	22	0	9	3	129
A	3-D	12.2	0.2	1.1	0.0	2.2	0.0	1.3	0.0	17.1
		55	1	5	0	10	0	6	0	77
	Total	52.8	1.1	6.0	2.2	27.7	0.2	9.1	0.9	100.0
		238	5	27	10	125	1	41	4	451
B	Workbook	23.1	10.3	5.0	9.9	0.4	0.8	0.0	0.0	49.6
		56	25	12	24	1	2	0	0	120
	Collage	7.4	2.1	12.4	8.7	0.0	0.4	0.4	0.0	31.4
		18	5	30	21	0	1	1	0	76
B	3-D	14.0	1.2	2.1	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	19.0
		34	3	5	3	0	0	1	0	46
	Total	44.6	13.6	19.4	19.8	0.4	1.2	0.8	0.0	100.0
		108	33	47	48	1	3	2	0	242
C	Workbook	15.2	0.	15.0	0.0	18.2	0.0	4.8	0.0	53.9
		94	4	93	0	113	0	30	0	334
	Collage	5.3	0.8	6.5	0.0	6.5	0.0	5.5	0.0	24.5
		33	5	40	0	40	0	34	0	152
C	3-D	5.2	0.0	1.3	0.0	8.9	0.0	6.3	0.0	21.6
		32	0	8	0	55	0	39	0	134
	Total	25.6	1.5	22.7	0.0	33.5	0.0	16.6	0.0	100.0
		159	9	141	0	208	0	103	0	620

A: Devices supporting learning, B: SNS based health services, C: Health care services of local hospitals

Table 6. Proportion and number of a type of consumer need elicited by each tool in the total

COMPARISONS AMONG TOOLS

The three generative tools are compared in terms of their contribution on eliciting the eight types of consumer needs. The consumer needs extracted with a tool are classified among the eight types of needs. Each row in (Table 7) indicates the proportions of eight types of consumer needs that are elicited by each tool.

Theme A and B in (Table 7) show that 3-D modeling elicits the IFR type the most, while theme C indicates that 3-D modeling elicits the XFR type a lot. Collages produce relatively more emotional needs such as the IER or IEO types as indicated in themes A and B. Workbooks are turned out to be dynamic in eliciting different types of consumer needs. Theme A indicates that workbooks are more likely to produce the functional improvable type of either internal or external,

while theme B and C show that workbooks also elicit the emotional and the empowering.

In summary, workbooks tend to elicit functional and improvable needs at the first stage of a generative study and they also catch emotional and empowering needs when they are applied to intangible services or to young generations. Collages are relatively good at eliciting emotional needs, while 3-D modeling is relatively good at eliciting functional needs in detail.

Theme / Tool	IFR	IFO	IER	IEO	XFR	XFO	XER	XEO	Total	
A	Workbook	45.3	1.6	3.3	0.4	38.0	0.4	10.6	0.4	100.0
	Collage	55.8	0.0	10.9	7.0	17.1	0.0	7.0	2.3	100.0
	3-D	71.4	1.3	6.5	0.0	13.0	0.0	7.8	0.0	100.0
	Total	52.8	1.1	6.0	2.2	27.7	0.2	9.1	0.9	100.0
B	Workbook	46.7	20.8	10.0	20.0	0.8	1.7	0.0	0.0	100.0
	Collage	23.7	6.6	39.5	27.6	0.0	1.3	1.3	0.0	100.0
	3-D	73.9	6.5	10.9	6.5	0.0	0.0	2.2	0.0	100.0
	Total	44.6	13.6	19.4	19.8	0.4	1.2	0.8	0.0	100.0
C	Workbook	28.1	1.2	27.8	0.0	33.8	0.0	9.0	0.0	100.0
	Collage	21.7	3.3	26.3	0.0	26.3	0.0	22.4	0.0	100.0
	3-D	23.9	0.0	6.0	0.0	41.0	0.0	29.1	0.0	100.0
	Total	25.6	1.5	22.7	0.0	33.5	0.0	16.6	0.0	100.0

A: Devices supporting learning, B: SNS based health services, C: Health care services of local hospitals

Table 7. Proportion of a type of consumer need in the total elicited by a tool

(Table 7) is graphically presented in (Figure 4) to show the distinguishable features of the results. The darker area above the horizontal line indicates that consumer needs originated internally, while the darker area below indicates that they originated externally. The darker area left of the vertical line, indicates that consumer needs are related with functional utility, while the darker to the right, shows that they are linked with emotional experience. The darker the inner circle, consumer needs are related with improvable solutions, while the darker the outer circle, they are related with enhancing an individual's capability.

The diagrams are much darker in the lefts of the inner circles except those of the SNS based health care services. This implies that, in general, consumer needs are focused within the boundaries of the

improvable and the functional, and these are most obvious in the tangible product case. On the other hand, teenagers' needs are intensively originated internally and expand to reach out beyond their capabilities. They reveal their willingness to be empowered in managing their own health care, while adults tend to have narrower scopes in revealing their needs regarding similar health care services.

Workbooks elicit relatively diverse types of consumer needs among the three tools, while collages tend to add up emotional needs. Three-D models tend to be supplementary for eliciting the functional, but expand the functional ideas in detail.

Figure 4. Comparing eight types of consumer needs elicited by each tool

DISCUSSION

Human-centered design uses many different tools and methods originated from various academic fields. Creating useful, usable, and desirable artifacts that peoples really need requires a deep understanding of consumer needs. Generative techniques are applied within several projects in searching Korean consumers' tacit and latent needs that are hardly explored with traditional research methods. Outcomes

of the applications are successful and are proved to be promising techniques for revealing the thoughts, ideas, desires, and dreams that are tacit and latent even in the shy and quiet Korean culture in which people hardly speak out.

The generative techniques allow participants to construct a view on the context of their living and the related experiences by calling up their memories of the past and by eliciting their hopes and desires of the present and dreams of the future. The techniques clearly differ from the conventional techniques that only offer a view on people's current and past experiences. The generative techniques give scope for learning potential future experiences by letting people reflect, re-live, and re-feel their experiences in each theme of a project and by exposing their thoughts, fears, ideas, aspirations, and dreams.

The revised three step procedure of a generative technique is suggested for revealing Korean consumers' needs that are seated deep in their minds. A project starts with an immersion or sensitization step with a daily self-documentation of a workbook for about a week. The next two steps take place in a face-to-face group workshop with four to five participants at a time with two to three groups in total. A group session starts with a storytelling about each participant's finished workbook individually and a group of participants gather together for the second step of activation and the third of dreaming. These procedures produce rich, live, and abundant transcriptions which contain all the storytelling and meaning of the activities in an excel file for each participant. Any clues containing consumer needs in each theme of a study are highlighted and listed in each participant's excel file. Mutually exclusive need statements are a good source of data for further analysis.

The data underlying this study draws on the author's previous three projects of searching consumer needs. The themes are university students' needs on devices supporting learning; SNS based health care service design for teenagers, and health care service design for local hospitals among adults. The statements containing any clues of consumer needs from the

three projects are repeatedly examined to accomplish the dual purposes of this study. Common dimensions of consumer needs are explored and the differences among the generative tools in eliciting consumer needs are examined.

Three layers of consumer needs are discovered through a time consuming search across the need statements of the three studies. The most obvious dimension is about the origin of a need either caused by one self or caused by surroundings of the self. This dimension is notated as a *source* either internal or external. The next obvious dimension is about the content of a need as either pursuing physical outcomes such as durability, usability, or usefulness or pursuing positive feelings or joyful experiences. This is depicted as a *utility* either functional or emotional. The last dimension takes the longest time to discover and it relates with need fulfilling methods regarding either the improvement of the current condition or the enhancement of an individual's capability. This is expressed as a *solution* either improvable or empowering.

The three dimensions, each with two alternatives, produce eight types of consumer needs by multiplying $2 \times 2 \times 2$. This study suggests *the tree dimensional eight type framework of consumer needs*. This framework is represented graphically with double circles with a horizontal and a vertical axis and the resulting eight spaces represent the eight types of consumer needs. The eight types of consumer needs are initialized as IFR (internal functional improvable), IFO (internal functional empowering), IER (internal emotional improvable), IEO (internal emotional empowering), XFR (external functional improvable), XFO (external functional empowering), XER (external emotional improvable), and XEO (external emotional empowering).

The graphical notation of the framework provides an effective way of understanding the characteristics of consumer needs at a glance that are elicited through gleaning grass-roots insights into both articulated and unarticulated consumer needs with totally bottom-up approaches. Applying the three dimensional eight type

framework of consumer needs to the three projects reveals that the source of a consumer need tend to be internal, the utility functional, and the solution improvable. University students' needs on a tangible product are mostly composed with IFR and XFR types, while teenagers' needs on health care services spread over internal (I) types and adults' needs on local hospitals are limited within the boundary of the improvable (R) type. The empowerment needs are barely revealed except in the teenagers' study. Teenagers' health care needs are mostly originated internally, so that external (X) types are almost never revealed.

About a week of the self-documentation regarding the workbook and 3-D modeling at a face-to-face group session produce a lot of functional (F) improvable (R) type needs while the latter expands the ideas in more detail. Collages produce relatively more emotional (E) needs. All three types of tools in sequence provide the stages for participants to grow their insights and foresights about a theme gradually.

The generative tools adopted in various projects in Korea lead to valuable findings in this study. However, analyzing the multi-layered fragmentary data is a very time-consuming task that requires a heightened sensitivity to emerging insights and patterns.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study met the dual objectives. They showed that (1) consumer needs are composed with three dimensions: internal versus external as the source of a need, functional versus emotional as a utility, and improvable versus empowering as a solution; (2) the three dimensions in combination produce eight types of consumer needs that are useful for understanding and comparing characteristics of consumer needs; (3) workbooks and 3-D modeling are good to elicit functional and improvable needs, while collages are good to extract emotional needs; (4) consumer needs on a tangible product are focused on functional improvable needs, while emotional needs appeared to be increased for services; and (5) the younger generation reveals their

desire for expand their capabilities, while adults' scopes are relatively limited within the boundary of feasible improvements.

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